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CLINICAL GUIDELINES FOR ENTRY LEVEL NURSE PRACTITIONER

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

In western society, cosmetic treatments have evolved into a mainstream phenomenon. Botulinum Toxin Type A (BTX) and facial fillers (FF) are proven cost effective alternatives for millions of Americans in search for a youthful appearance without the expensive cost of surgery, complication, and downtime associated with invasive surgical procedures. The steady increase of the consumer market and the number of minimally invasive procedures being performed within the past few years indicates a foreseen increase in the number of complications. Currently in the U.S. there is no standardized accreditation process to regulate the practice of aesthetic medicine. The development of a clinical guideline for non-invasive cosmetic treatments was developed for entry-level nurse practitioner to facilitate appropriate technique, accurate formulation and dosage for optimal therapeutic outcomes. Three experts in the field of cosmetic injectables with two years or more experience independently evaluated the potential impact of evidence based practice (EBP) clinical practice guidelines (CPG) to assess potential patient outcomes, provider satisfaction, efficiency, and potential patient safety impact. The scores were used to compute the scale context validity index (S-CVI) to predict relevance of this project through expert assessment. For the Facial Rejuvenation Tool (FRT) assessment tool 6 out of 7 items were evaluated as strongly or agreeable recommendations by three experts, which resulted in S-CVI of 0.85. For the CPGs 7 out of 7 items were evaluated as strongly or agreeable recommendations by three experts,

which resulted in S-CVI of 1.00. Based on three expert evaluations of the FRT and CPGs, there is high necessity to implement CPG into practice

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BACKGROUND

Cosmetic Botox and FF are temporary treatments to help mitigate the aging process. The FDA approved Botox and FF in early 2000s for the treatment of temporarily softening the frown lines between the eyebrows and crows' feet in patients 18 to 65 years of age, and temporarily treating facial fat loss such as, nasiolabial folds. However, there are many non-approved by the FDA (off labeled) usages of cosmetic Botox, such as: treatment of frontalis muscle, smile lift, eyebrow lift, nasalis lines, orbicularis oris (smoker lines), platysmal bands, etc. (FDA, 2015). New product development and improved commercial availability has led to new advancements in treatment options for noninvasive cosmetic enhancement (Coleman & Carruthers, 2006).

In 2015, Americans spent over 13.5 billion dollars on surgical and non-surgical procedures. Cosmetic surgical procedures accounted for 58% and non-invasive cosmetic procedures (botox, filler, hair removal, chemical peels, and microdermabrasion) accounted for 42% of revenue in 2015. In addition, there was a 1.5 billion dollar increase in combined surgical and non-surgical procedures from 2014 to 2015 (ASPS, 2015). In accordance to the increase in revenue, nonsurgical procedures have increased by 44% in the past five years. Furthermore, injectables including: Botox, Dysport, Xeomin Juvederm, Perlane, Radiesse, Restylane, and Voluma saw a 21% increase in 2015. Since, 2009 there has been a steady increase in the number of individuals who undergo Botox and FF treatments.

Appropriate guidelines are imperative for midlevel practitioner in the aesthetic field. The increase of public awareness and acceptance of minimally invasive procedures,

such as Botox and FF, increases the size of the consumer market. Therefore, indicating a foreseen increase in the number of complications (Funt & Pavicic, 2013).

Nurse practitioners (NP) are in high demand within aesthetic medicine based on their scope of practice to autonomously perform mandatory history and physical for new patients (Medical Board of California, 2012). Nurse practitioners are providing the majority of these minimally invasive procedures without a governing state regulatory board for medical spas or evidence based clinical guidelines. Patient safety is left to the discretion of individual cosmetic provider, i.e. doctor, NPs, physician assistants (PAs), or nurse (licensed vocational nurse [LVN] or registered nurse [RN]). Currently in the U.S. there is no standardized accreditation process to regulate the practice of aesthetic medicine. Many aesthetic practitioners are not efficiently trained to administer aesthetic procedures. This may result in poor patient outcomes. The practice of aesthetic medicine should not be exempted from structured training, accreditation, and practice guidelines, which ultimately serves to protect the public and cosmetic provider from maleficence and non-evidence based practice (FDA, 2012).

Pharmacokinetics of Botox

Botox, derived from a bacterium called *Clostridium botulinum*, binds to motor neuron terminals to inhibit the release of acetylcholine and prevent the muscle from contracting. Although most common side effects include: headache, erythema, and bruising; serious life threatening side effect can occur hours to days after injection. Generally, overtreatment causes the BTX toxin to spread to distant muscle compromising the ability of the muscle to function normally, also known as botulism. Botulism can lead

to loss of strength and muscle weakness, double vision, blurred vision, hoarseness, loss of bladder control, and trouble breathing and swallowing (FDA, 2012).

There are numerous contraindications for Botox administration listed by the FDA, which include concomitant administration with quinine, calcium channel blockers, penicillamine, or aminoglycoside antibiotics. Drug interaction between these medications and Botox causes an anticholinergic effect, which results in the spread of neurotoxins to distant muscles. Another contraindication for Botox involves the administration of Botox to pregnant or breastfeeding women. Botox is a category C drug, which may result in unknown adverse effect on the fetus or baby (FDA, 2016). Proper education to childbearing aged women is imperative to prevent harmful effects from reaching the fetus or infant (Coleman & Carruthers, 2006). Lastly, those with neuromuscular diseases or peripheral neuropathy are strictly prohibited from receiving Botox treatment based on the possibility of further weakening neuromuscular function (Coleman & Carruthers, 2006).

Pharmacokinetics of FF

Unlike BTX, facial fillers are temporary absorbable injectable implants, such as Juvederm, Perlane, Radiesse, Restylane, and Voluma. These FDA approved fillers are chemically formulated to include one of the four following ingredients, collagen, hyaluronic acid (HA), calcium hydroxylapatite, and poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) used to treat nasolabial folds, cheeks, and lips. Collagen filler, a purified collagen, derived from a cow (bovine); collagen has the shortest lasting therapeutic effect of three to four months. Hyaluronic acid is a polysaccharide present in human tissue. The gel form of HA swells, causing a smoothing and filling effect. This filler is formed from bacteria and chemically modified to have a longer lasting effect, approximately six to 12 months. The mineral

commonly found in human teeth and bones is called Calcium hydroxylapatite. This mineral is developed in a gel like solution and injected into wrinkles for a smoothing effect lasting, approximately, 18 months. Lastly, PLLA is a biodegradable man made polymer the longest lasting filler, two years, given over a series of treatments. Common side effects to these four fillers include: bruising, redness, swelling, pain, and itching. Adverse reactions, however less common, include necrosis, sore at injection site, allergic reaction, infection, keloids, injury to blood supply, permanent hard nodules, and stroke. Moreover, FF are contraindicated in patients with bleeding disorder and severe allergy history. Allergy history could include, allergies to eggs, collagen, animal products, bacteria, or lidocaine (FDA, 2012).

Problem Statement

Currently there is a paucity of literature providing adequate standards for evidence-based practice (EBP). The objective for this project was to develop clinical practice guidelines for the administration of Botox and FF for entry-level nurse practitioners, defined as those with less than six months of experience in a medical spa or primary setting. A medical spa is a treatment facility which provides medical grade treatment such as; Botox, fillers, and laser treatments. This guideline provide recommendations for 1) assessment 2) injection techniques, 3) treatment plan for gender, race, and anatomical structure, 4) contraindications and adverse complications.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to develop guidelines for entry level NPs to competently administer Botox and facial fillers in a medical spa or primary care setting. The development of a clinical guideline for non-invasive cosmetic treatments would

facilitate accurate formulation and dosage for optimal therapeutic outcomes for every patient. Optimal patient outcomes in the cosmetic setting is endorsed by the NP's ability to provide competent consultation yielding realistic patient treatment goals (ASPS, 2016). The stakeholders are plastic surgeons, dermatologist, primary physicians, pharmaceutical representatives, registered nurses, physician assistants, nurse practitioners, medical spas, and patients.

The following objectives would be used to facilitate the development of clinical guidelines.

Objectives:

1. Developing a wrinkle and facial volume loss assessment scales
2. Complete a table of evidence (TOE) framework to analyze EBP articles on Botox and FF injections.
3. Integrate evidence-based technique, treatment regimen, and post treatment care into clinical practice guidelines (CPGs).

Needs Assessment

Currently, in California, a medical director acting as a supervisor of noninvasive cosmetic medicine is not required to have previous training in dermatology or plastic surgery (Medical Board of California, 2014). Nurse practitioners under the supervision of a physician with no prior cosmetic experience are liable for poor patient outcome and adverse complications. To learn the actual procedures (e.g., injecting neurotoxins and facial fillers/volume enhancers), a NP should seek mentorship among knowledgeable advanced NPs, registered nurses, or physician in the field of cosmetic medicine. An advanced NP is a practitioner with more than one-year experience in the field of cosmetic

medicine (The American Society of Plastic Surgical Nurses [ASPSN], 2015). A clinical guideline for best practice with Botox and FFs would improve quality and consistency in patient outcomes and reduce the occurrence of side effects and adverse complications (Brennan, 2015).

Recognizing the strength, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) analysis was used to determine the significance of implementing a clinical guideline for novice NP administering Botox and FF. The strengths of creating a clinical guideline included: reduction in variation of treatment, improvement in consistency in patient outcomes, availability to supplemental educational resources, adequate patient consultation and post care teaching, and reduction or elimination of adverse events, and improved self-confidence for novice NPs. The weaknesses include the evidence used to support clinical guideline may be misinterpreted or have misleading findings. Opportunities for this implementation include: a guide for new providers, and collaborating with pharmaceutical companies to standardize a treatment plan. Associated threats might include: patient non-adherence and lack of collaborative partnerships from providers, business owners, nurses, and advanced NPs. The desired outcome for this project was to develop clinical guidelines that would improve patient satisfaction, decrease adverse events, and improve NP competency for Botox and FF treatment.

Supporting Framework

According to Polit & Beck (2012), the presence of a theoretical framework guides the development process of a research project and highlights key concepts and rationalize acceptable outcome. This project used two supporting frameworks. One framework, a portion of the John Hopkins Evidence Base Practice Model (JHEBPM) was used to guide

the synthesis of the research articles and to develop a table of evidence (TOE). The other framework, the Ace Star Model of Knowledge Transformation model (ASMKT) was used to guide the development of clinical guidelines for this project. The weakness of the ASMKT model is the inability to rate the quality and level of evidence of each study. The John Hopkins's evidence level and quality guideline tool was incorporated into this project to compensate for the lack of quality and evidence based rating tool in the ASMKT model (Stevens, 2004). The collaboration of these two models provided synergy in the development of a quality EBP clinical guideline.

John Hopkins's Evidence Level and Quality Guideline

A vital attribute of the JHNEBP models is the evidence and quality guidance tool. This tool provides an accessible, user-friendly process of grading evidence and quality levels research (Frank, 2014). John Hopkins's evidence level and quality guideline is an accessible resource to use for study selection; the transparent and straightforward approach helps navigate through the data collection process. Steps for appraising studies are categorized by research and non-research evidence. The appraisals of research and non-research studies are analyzed for their strength and quality level. Using an I-V scale to determine the strength of the evidence, with Level 1 the strongest, and Level V the weakest, executes the process used to appraise the strength. In addition, a second scale for quality determines the rate of quality evidence by rating each study as high, good, or low. In the clinical guideline section, every study was appraised for strength and evidence quality (Newhouse, Dearholt, & Poe, 2007).

Table 1

John Hopkins Nursing Evidence Base Practice and Quality Guide

Evidence Levels	Quality Guide
Level I Experimental study, randomized controlled trial (RCT), Systematic Review of RCTs, with or without meta-analysis	High Quality Consistent, generalizable; sufficient sample size for the study design; adequate control; definitive conclusions; consistent recommendations based on comprehensive literature review that includes thorough reference to scientific evidence.
Level II Quasi-experimental study Systematic review of a combination of RCTs and quasi-experimental, or quasi-experimental studies only, with or without meta-analysis.	Good Quality Reasonably consistent results; sufficient sample size for the study design; some control, fairly definitive conclusions; reasonably consistent recommendation based on fairly comprehensive literature review that includes some references to scientific evidence.
Level III Non-experimental study Systematic review of a combination of RCTs, quasi-experimental, and non-experimental studies, or non-experimental studies only, with or without meta-analysis Qualitative study or systematic review with or without a meta-synthesis.	Low Quality or Major Flaw Little evidence with inconsistent results; insufficient sample size for the study design; conclusion cannot be drawn

The Ace Star Model of Knowledge Transformation

There is a cyclical process that directs the sequence of knowledge translation within the ASMKT model. The five essential stages of the model include: discovery, summary, translation, integration, and evaluation. In order for noninvasive cosmetic procedures in United States (U.S.) to reflect best evidence practice, there has to be an

understanding of the complexity of knowledge, including volume, and the form of available knowledge.

The Star Model, used for the project guidelines, includes five processes: discovery, evidence summary, translation, integration, and evaluation. These five processes were used to translate EBP studies into a clinical guideline. The premise of The Ace Star Model of Knowledge Transformation (ASMKT) is to translate evidence based knowledge produced by primary studies into a clinical decision making resource (Stevens, 2012). The ASMKT model is centered on the ability to guide in the synthesis and integration of quality evidence based research articles into guidelines, but also the integration of evidence guidelines into practice and the evaluation of recommended guidelines. Therefore, the ASMKT was an appropriate framework to guide the development of a standardized clinical guideline.

The Star Model of Knowledge Transformation was used to synthesize and convert knowledge obtained from primary studies, delineate a rigorous systematic review of research, and provide best practice recommendations to change clinical outcomes through EBP (Stevens, 2012). The development of clinical guideline for novice NPs promotes consistent quality of care and optimal patient outcomes. The model and guideline tool from the JHEBPM assisted in conducting a rigorous evaluation of research studies.

Figure 1. Star Model of Knowledge Transformation.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

The theory behind aging is described as a genetically preordained process accelerated by environmental damages. Ramos et al (2013) supports the general theory of aging by characterizing the aging process into two variables, intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Intrinsic aging includes: ethnicity, anatomic variation, and hormonal changes. Extrinsic aging includes: ambient conditions, drugs, smoking, and sunlight exposure. The combination of intrinsic and extrinsic factor contributes to the normal process of facial maturation. Moreover, facial aging also involves the loss of structural support over time. Gravity in conjunction with volume loss of facial fat in the midface results in downward migration of fat compartments, leading to deepening of nasolabial folds, hollowness beneath the eyes, and static wrinkles (Few, Mitragotri, & Murphy, 2014).

Static and dynamic are two characteristics used to describe facial wrinkles. Static wrinkles are present at rest, when not performing facial expressions, and dynamic wrinkles are present during facial expressions. Biological and environmental factors are the likely contributor to static wrinkles caused by the aging process by gradually decreasing collagen and elastic fibers that affect skin elasticity and facial volume. The administration of BTX and FF corrects the effect of aging by restoring volume and relaxing the facial muscle movement (Coleman & Carruthers, 2006).

According to Ramos et al. (2013), aging produces various changes to the face, beginning from childhood, which matures from a rounded angelic face into an angular face with defined features, which will continue to transform through teenager years to adult life. Rabe et al. (2006), reported modern society's perception of age and beauty is

largely dependent on the largest organ in the body, the skin. Rabe et al. (2006) also supports the basic biological process involved in aging is related to the reduction in function and the ability to tolerate injury. Ramos et al. (2013) suggested extrinsic and intrinsic aging factors should be considered when developing a treatment plan for patients.

Rabe et al. (2006) and Ramos et al. (2013) outlined the current treatments for aging skin into three categories: primary, secondary, and tertiary therapies. The primary approach aims to protect the skin from sun damage with chemical or physical broad-spectrum sun filters, such as: sunscreen or hats. Ramos et al. (2013) characterized sun exposure to induce a surge of molecular and cellular changes that trigger atrophy, skin disorders, and structural changes. Rabe et al. (2006) endorses sun protection as the most cost effective anti-aging therapy that can be offered to patients. The damages of sunlight on the skin is devastating and represent 90% of visible aging facial characteristics, mainly seen in lighter pigmented patients. The primary approach goal is to prevent the occurrence of photo aging.

Secondary approach aims to postpone or reduce signs of aging by using retinoic acid, antioxidants, estrogens, and growth factors. In Rabe et al. (2006), the systematic review of literature reported retinol and antioxidant as key to reversing the effect of photodamage; whereas estrogen and growth factor are essential treatments of dryness and wrinkled skin. In Ramos et al. (2013), a double-blinded systematic review showed hormone replacement therapy as a reversal for loss of skin elasticity, increased skin hydration, and thickness in women.

Lastly, the tertiary approach involves a more abrasive approach. The use of chemical peels with high acid concentration, lasers, and the injection of FF and BTX are used to reverse and treat the aging presentation. The tertiary approach's main premise is to treat serious signs of aging. In the past, tertiary treatment was considered the last resort. However, Rabe et al. (2006) reports chemical peels, lasers, Botox, and FF are becoming more popular and desirable because of its use to treat both intrinsic and extrinsic aging, as well as cosmetic facial enhancement. Although there are three therapeutic treatment categories for aging skin, this project focused on tertiary therapy treatment recommendation, such as Botox and FF.

In the cosmetic field, many tertiary, noninvasive procedures, and commercially used materials claim to provide improvement in skin texture and presentation. However, in several research studies, BTX and FF are the only treatments used to quantifiably mitigate wrinkles and restore volume and youthfulness to a patient's face. Therefore, based on this quantifiable outcome this project focused the literature review on standard clinical guideline to aide in the treatment plan for entry-level NPs for the administration of Botox and FF in a medical spa setting. The effect of BTX and FF provide a remarkable enhancement to facial youthfulness by restoring smooth and fuller facial features (Ramos et al, 2013).

The injection of BTX (Botox, Dysport, and Xeomin) and FF (Juvederm Perlane, Radiesse, Voluma, and Restylane) is now established as two of the top five nonsurgical procedures in 2015. Botox, Dysport, and Xeomin are neurotoxin used to weaken a specific facial muscle to reduce signs of rhytids also known as wrinkles, however, Botox is the number one procedure nationwide (The American Society of Plastic Surgeons

(ASPS), 2015). In contrast, FF, Juvaderm, Perlane, Radiesse, Voluma, and Restylane rejuvenate the skin by correcting volume loss in deepened rhytids or restores volume in depleted facial anatomical structures (Carruthers, 2008). BTX and FF can be used as monotherapy or as combined therapy depending on the severity of facial elasticity and malar fat volume loss (Coleman & Carruthers, 2006). The ability to differentiate between which product or products to use is based on product knowledge and understanding of patient's ideal outcome goals. A clear understanding of the differences among products of the same class is imperative in the clinical treatment of wrinkles and facial volume loss. BTX and FF are produced in many formulations; however, Carruthers et al. (2008) reported that both, Botox and Hyaluronic Acid Filler (HAF) are the product of choice for positive patient outcomes.

Patient care is dependent on NPs having competencies in knowledge and technique when administering cosmetic treatment to the general public. Monheit (2015) reports the FDA approved 3 BTX for the treatment of the upper face, including onabotulinum toxin (Botox), abotulinum toxin (Dysport), and incobotulinum toxin (Xeomin). Botox and dysport are the two common BTX formulations used in the U.S. Botox is considered the safest and most effective, and less likely to diffuse, and the only BTX FDA approved for the treatment of glabella and lateral canthal lines. Dysport was FDA approved in 2009 and has a safe patient profile, earlier onset of efficacy, and lasts longer than Botox, however, it is more likely to spread and cause ptosis of the eye when used in the upper region of face, and is also difficult for novice practitioners to administer without poor patient outcomes. Dysport and Botox both inhibit the calcium-mediated release of acetylcholine, the weight of the neurotoxins are both the same; however, there

is a difference in molecular weight of botulinum toxin/hemagglutinin complex. The difference in molecular weight causes Dysport to migrate more than Botox (Monheit, 2015). In a triple blind RCT, Kassir et al. (2013) found Botox provided a safer and effective treatment than Dysport and less likely to cause eye or eyebrow ptosis.

The FDA (2008) approved synthetic (nonabsorbable) and natural (absorbable) fillers for the enhancement of facial tissue. Synthetic fillers include, Radiesse and Sculptra. Natural fillers include, HAF and collagen fillers. Carruthers et al. (2008) outlined HAF excellent safety profile and requirement of no allergy skin test before treatment. Complications from HAF can be avoided by careful technique and adverse complication can be reversed by injection of hyaluronidase, not available for other synthetic or natural fillers (Coleman & Carruthers, 2006). McCracken (2006) reported HAF has been clinically shown to provide improvement and longer lasting effect than collagen fillers. The assurance of patient satisfaction is based on product knowledge and individualizing treatment plan to rejuvenate skin appearance, enhance volume loss, and incorporate patient's desires (Carruthers et al, 2008). Carruthers et al. (2008) reported botox and HAF as the product of choice for positive patient outcomes. The tertiary treatment of botox and HAF were the two products discussed in this literature review for the recommendations of clinical guidelines.

Standard Clinical Practice Guidelines

The Joint Commission describes patient safety as providing safe and effective care of the highest quality and value. The institute of Medicine (IOM) advocates that healthcare must be provided in safe, effective, timely, patient centered, efficient and equitable manner (IOM, 2001). Clinical guidelines would better protect patients in a

medical spa setting from the risk of non-invasive cosmetic procedures. Keogh (2013) highlighted the importance of practitioners understanding infection control, facial anatomy and muscle function, drug delivery, and medical emergencies when administer Botox and FF.

Kredo et al. (2016) explained clinical guidelines as recommendation intended to optimize quality patient care based on informed evidence based research and assessment. The implementation of CPGs in a medical spa setting for entry-level practitioner could be used to guide clinical decision-making for substantiates positive patient outcomes. Kleier (2015) identifies CPGs as best clinical evidence routinely used to provide a roadmap to guide physician and other healthcare providers in the proper treatment of common medical disorders and clinical circumstances. A clinical practice guideline for the use of BTX and FF includes, a patient assessment facial tool to govern the treatment plan of technique and dosage, patient teaching, and care of adverse events. The focus entails the upper face (forehead, crows' feet, and glabellar) for the use of Botox, and the nasiolabial and mid face region for FF.

Assessment

The literature discussed patient assessment should include the identification of biological and environmental facial damage. Facial aging is the effect of intrinsic and extrinsic factors; these two factors lead to thinning of the skin, wrinkle formation, and loss of volume (Ramos et al, 2013). Rzany et al. (2012) reports the key characteristics for visible facial aging include: forehead lines, crows' feet, glabellar lines, eyebrow ptosis, loss of cheek volume, nasolabial folds, marionette lines, wrinkling of the perioral vermillion border, thinning of the lips, sagging neck lines, and loss of chin definition.

An in-depth patient assessment should include an aesthetic scale for wrinkle and facial volume loss. However, ethnicity, age, and gender should also be included in patient assessment for facial treatment. In a study by Brandt et al. (2009), women were more likely to respond to Botox than men. In Brandt et al. (2009) double blind random control trial (RCT) at day 30 in the BTX group for women investigator observed a 93% response in therapeutic effect and in men a 67% response in therapeutic effect with 50 units of BTX. Brandt et al. (2009) based findings on the fact that men having a greater muscle mass than women, which requires a higher dose.

Brandt et al. (2009) also found subjects aged 50 years and older had a lower degree of efficacy for Botox treatment than those younger than 50. Consistent with Brandt et al. (2009), Guo et al. (2015) suggests skin type, ethnicity, degree of photo damage, age, sex, and severity of wrinkles at rest and at maximum contraction may affect treatment outcomes. Likewise, the use of a numeric facial scale and a focused facial assessment aids patient consultation and development of a treatment plan to provide optimal patient outcomes by the NP (Rzany et al., 2012).

A systematic classification of photoaging, elasticity, kinetic lines and facial volume loss can be assessed through quantitative methods such as scales (Glogau, 1996). Rzany et al. (2012) suggests a comprehensive face evaluation centered on age related changes can help identify important areas for treatment and provide optimal individual treatment strategies. Carruther et al. (2012) suggest implementing aesthetic scale into clinical practice provides a valuable tool for validating need of facial enhancement and evaluating the success of aesthetic treatment. Carruthers (2012) conducted a study to objectively assess the validity and reliability of three 5-point rating photonumeric scales

of the midface. The three 5-point photonumeric rating scales were found to be reliable for valid and reproducible assessment of the midface. Carruther et al. (2008) forehead lines and (2012) crows' feet 5-point photonumeric scale was highly significant in depicting the common severity lines seen in patient seeking corrective treatment. Kim et al. (2004) The Rated Numeric Kinetic Lines Scale (RNKLS) was developed to grade facial wrinkles secondary to hyperkinetic lines. The RNKLS demonstrated moderate to substantial reliability with high statistical significance Rzany et al. (2012) The Global Face Assessment Scale was found to help identify important areas of facial aging and to define optimal aesthetic treatment strategies.

The five numeric scales effectively assessed age related facial changes; however, these numeric scales were limited to only wrinkles or facial volume. Therefore, a comprehensive objective tool allowing the assessment and facial rejuvenation treatment of various age related changes was developed. The development of a user-friendly accessible midface wrinkle and volume loss adjunctive treatment tool enhanced the clinical practice guideline (Rzany et al., 2012). This adjunctive tool is called "The Facial Rejuvenation Tool."

The Facial Rejuvenation Tool (FRT) assesses aging signs and severity among different facial regions as well as, provides recommendation for treatment based on gender and ethnicity. This objective tool allows the NP to assess baseline and develop treatment outcomes for any type of facial rejuvenations concerning the upper to midface region. The FRT is an easy to follow, time sparing scoring tool, uses comprehensive scales to measure aging characteristics, such as wrinkles and volume loss. This tool is customized to incorporate evidence based wrinkle pattern and midface regions for

volume augmentation. The commonly found wrinkle pattern of the upper face includes, glabella, frontalis, and crows' feet. Based on evidence-based research on wrinkle patterns this tool outlined muscle activity, the number of injection sites per wrinkle pattern, and recommended treatment dosage. In addition, the FRT tool also outlines assessment and treatment options for facial fillers which include, anatomical region for the midface, injection sites, and recommended dosages based on region.

The treatment recommendations provided for this tool is based on evidence based practice and consensus among experts. Treatment dosages are customized to include gender and ethnicity specific recommendations. However, there was paucity in the literature between the African American (AA) and Hispanic population. In contrast, expert consensus and evidence-based research detailed the recommendations for Caucasian, Asians, and gender differences. As recommended in the literature males need an increase dose in the glabella region due to the strength and muscle mass of the glabella in males (Carruthers, Glogau, & Blitzer, 2013). Furthermore, the Asian population will require fewer doses within the upper face due to preferences of a natural look, and fewer wrinkles (Wu et al., 2015). In contrast, volume restoration is considered based only on gender differences. Proper technique is warranted when treating males and females to refrain from feminizing the male patient or masculinizing the female patient (Muhn et al., 2012).

Facial validity for the FRT tool was supported by current consensus recommendations and the saturation in literature of the reliability of the five scales adopted for this tool. Therefore, the FRT was implemented into the clinical practice

guideline for novice NPs as adjunctive user-friendly tool to assess and recommend individualized treatments (La Padula et al., 2016).

Adverse events and Contraindications

Identifying and mitigating adverse complication is an essential factor in aesthetic treatment competency. Therefore, it is imperative that common side effects of Botox are recognized such as: swelling, bruising, and ptosis of the eyelid. Fortunately, these common side effects are temporary requiring no adjunctive treatment. Other rare side effect includes flu like symptoms and headache (Brandt et al., 2009). The FDA (2008) reports side effects for HAF as, swelling, bruising, and necrosis of tissue. The necrosis of tissue is the only important adverse event for NPs to identify and treat immediately. The necrosis of facial tissue occurs when a vascular artery is punctured and injected with HAF. The disruption of the vascular artery leads to poor blood supply to adjacent tissue. If blanching, duskiness, or necrosis occurs, the immediate use of hyaluronidase should be administered as close to injection as possible (Grunebaum, 2009). Kim et al. (2011) reports no benefit of injecting hyaluronidase the day after HA filler injection. A common understanding of facial anatomy, areas of facial aging, and safety-standardized technique reduces the occurrence of adverse event for patient outcomes.

It is important for the NP to understand the contraindication for Botox and HAF. Overall, Botox and HAF have a safe and effective profile. The FDA (2008) contraindication for HAF includes: history of anaphylaxis and bleeding disorders. A warning should also be advised for infection or inflammation of the involved area, a history of herpes, which may cause a reactivation of symptoms, and patients susceptible

to keloid formation or hyperpigmentation. To avoid and manage complication of the face, general precaution should be followed.

Carruthers (2008) advises to avoid the use of Botox in the malar smile lines. Injection in this area can cause a stroke like appearance or distort the patient's smile. Treatment should be started conservatively with Botox and HAF to avoid over treatment; touchups can follow after two weeks. The FDA (2008) advises to prescribe antiviral drugs one week before treatment for Botox or HAF to prevent herpes symptoms reactivation. Carruthers (2008) recommends the oral administration of 1 g of valacyclovir on the day of treatment; prescription for valacyclovir as needed. Lastly, Feng et al. (2014) instructs to maintain a 1-centimeter (cm) distance from the orbital rim when injection Botox to avoid ptosis.

Treatment Plan

Shamban (2015) supports the necessity to design an injection or treatment approach that addresses the unique needs of each individual patient. The treatment plan for Botox and HAF should be customized to the patient's facial assessment, age, and ethnic background. Monheit (2015) suggest treatment plan should be tailored on an individual basis to achieve patient satisfaction. In younger adults monotherapy with Botox or HAF alone is usually effective, however, mid-aged adults may need a combination of Botox and FF to correct static and dynamic rhytides caused by photoaging (Coleman & Carruthers, 2006). In addition, individualized treatment plan should be tailored to include race and cultural ideals of beauty. In 2006 ethnic minorities accounted for 22% of all non-invasive cosmetic procedures in the U.S (Carruthers et al, (2006). Caucasian aesthetic beauty ideals should not be used as a standard treatment plan.

Every ethnic group possesses a different process pattern of aging such as; the Asian population tends to suffer from deflation in lips, as they grow older. A proper treatment goal would be to restore volume. Lastly, African Americans exhibit loss of volume in midface with age and have heavier cheeks. Proper treatment plan would involve malar augmentation instead of treating nasolabial folds usually presenting an unnatural look. Carruthers, Glogau, and Blitzler (2008) suggest the aging profile for Asian, African Americans, and Caucasians may affect the treatment plan. A meta-analysis conducted by Guo et al. (2015) suggests skin type, ethnicity, degree of photo damage, age, sex, and severity of wrinkles at rest and maximum contraction at treatment initiation may affect treatment outcome. Factors to evaluate before performing treatment include: the anatomy of the muscle, patient's muscle strength, baseline asymmetries, severity of rhytides, also known as wrinkles, the severity of facial volume, and most importantly the patient's desired outcome (Shamban, 2015).

Core competencies in Botox and FF should be met before any NP is able to treat a patient. All nurses and NPs should demonstrate competency in performing a complete aesthetic evaluation and have a thorough understanding of the patient's goals consistent with realistic outcomes (Monheit, 2015). It is the responsibility of cosmetic practitioners to enhance beauty and not distort. To accomplish desired outcome for patients, NPs need to possess empirical knowledge of facial anatomy, understand the interactions of fillers and neurotoxins on tissue and muscles, and possess competencies in technique and treatment plans (Shamban, 2015).

In summary, injectable Botox and FF are the treatment of choice to combat the signs of aging and restore a youthful appearance to patients of different gender, ethnicity,

and age. In addition, these two injectable products can be used alone or in combination treatment. Therefore, properly assessing patient's facial features and intrinsic factor, as well as, possessing empirical knowledge of various products, dosage, and administration technique determines the efficacy and patient satisfaction of treatment and is imperative to provide safe patient outcome. A thorough good faith exam and quality patient teaching decreases the risk of life threatening complications. It is vital for NPs to be competent in which conditions and medications are contraindicated and pose a risk to patients. A clinical practice guideline lays the foundation for NPs to function autonomously in a medical spa or primary practice setting.

METHOD

The FDA recommended tertiary treatment of Botox and HAF was used to develop clinical guidelines for the 18 to 65-year-old age group. The recommended age group provided by the FDA was adopted as part of the clinical practice guidelines. This guideline addressed the clinical practice of NPs in the treatment of Botox and HAF. The methods for this project included the use of the ASMKT. In accordance with a systematic review, the JHNEBP's evidence level and quality guideline was used to guide the table of evidence (TOE). This section contains: search strategy, TOE, evidence quality assessment, and expert evaluation.

Search Methods

New innovation pathways are essential to implement or integrate CPGs into practice. A search through the five databases was conducted for appraisal of literature included: Pubmed, Science direct Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health literature (CINAHL), EBSCO, and Cochrane library. In addition, direct online journals such as; American Society of Plastic Surgery (ASPS), The Food and Drug Administration (FDA), The American Society for Dermatology Surgery, Plastic Surgery Nursing, The American Journal of Plastic Surgeons, and Dermatology Therapy journal will also be used in the discovery process. Search terms included: cosmetic dermatology, soft fillers, dermal fillers, and cosmetic botulinum, anti-aging, and skin rejuvenation. Search limitation included journals published from 2006 to 2016 and English language. Inclusion criteria will include treatment of forehead, glabella, and crows' feet with the use of Botox and the nasiolabial and lip enhancement with the use of Hyaluronic fillers. Exclusion from search included publications involved in any other non-invasive

treatment that was not Botox such as, micro needling, platelet rich plasma (PRP) facials, facial laser treatments, or skin care products. A secondary search was conducted for wrinkle and/or volume loss scales and guidelines for injections.

Table of Evidence

In accordance with the Ace Star Model, a systematic and integrative review was conducted using the Cochrane Collaboration Database and Pubmed. A review of literature was used to identify the influential concepts surrounding Botox and HAF. This process provided access to a wealth of knowledge on the topic of Botox and HAF by synthesizing known knowledge into a single meaningful statement. This project constructed a clinical guideline that was validated by a TOE from an integrative and systematic literature review for the administration of Botox and HAF for novice NPs.

Evidence Based and Quality Guide

The translation of evidence into guideline was accomplished through adopting the John Hopkins Evidence Based and Quality guideline to evaluate the strength and evidence of articles in the TOE. Every study in the TOE was graded for level and quality of evidence. This project only adopted level I, II, III, IV, and V and high and good, quality evidence into clinical guidelines. Evidence from the Table of Evidence (TOE) guided the recommendations for assessment and injection techniques; 2) dosages for gender, race, and anatomical structure, 3) patient teaching 4) and adverse complication treatment for novice or beginner NPs. Dosage guidelines were specific to gender, age, and wrinkle or volume loss facial scale assessment.

The focus population is nurse practitioner with six months or less experience in injectable administration. The areas that were addressed in this project included: The

assessment and treatment of forehead, glabella, and crows' feet with the use of Botox; and assessment and treatment of the midface with the use of Hyaluronic fillers. Directing attention to novice practitioner increases the adoption of new innovation due to a lack of pre-established old habits (Saunders, 2015).

Evaluation of Outcome

Evidence base practice is intended to revolutionize healthcare by directing healthcare to a path where there is a high likelihood for producing intended health outcomes (Stevens, 2013). Therefore, a minimum of two experts in the field of cosmetic injectables with two years or more experience independently evaluated the potential impact of EBP CPG by using an ordinal evaluation tool to assess potential patient outcomes, provider satisfaction, efficiency, and potential patient safety impact. The scores from the evaluation scale were used to compute the context validity index to predict relevance of this project through expert assessment (Polit & Beck, 2012).

Ethical Implication

A fundamental component of conducting research is beneficence and nonmaleficence. These two ethical principles protect patient from physical and psychological harm. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) is the governing ethics board, which ensures the treatment of study participants (Polit & Beck, 2012). A petition was submitted to California State University, Los Angeles's (CSULA) IRB for a waiver based on no human subjects were used to develop this CPG.

Expert Evaluation

Of the three expert evaluators, two were mid-level practitioner such as a NP and physician assistant (PA) and one registered nurse (RN). Their experience in the aesthetic

industry ranged from two years to eight years. The reliability and the validity of the FRT assessment tool and CPGs were measured using the scale-level content validity index (S-CVI). CVI is defined as “. . . the extent to which an instrument adequately samples the research domain of interest when attempting to measure phenomena” (Wynd, Schmidt, & Schaefer, 2003, pg. 509). A four-point ordinal rating scale was used to evaluate the experts’ agreement to clinical recommendations and FRT: 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = agree, 4 = strongly agree. Then, the S-CVI was used to determine if the FRT and CPG were relevant to improve potential patient outcomes, provider satisfaction, efficiency, and potential patient safety.

Based on the S-CVI definition three evaluators have to agree on individual items in order to show relevance (Polit & Beck, 2006). For the FRT assessment tool 6 out of 7 items were evaluated as strongly or agreeable recommendations by three experts, and so the S-CVI is computed to be 0.85. For the CPGs 7 out of 7 items were evaluated as strongly or agreeable recommendations by three experts, and so the S-CVI is computed to be 1.00. Many researchers agree that an S-CVI of 0.80 or higher is deemed acceptable to measure relevance of content (Davis, 1992; Grand & Davis, 1997; Polit & Beck, 2004). Based on three expert evaluations of the FRT and CPGs, there is high necessity to implement CPG into practice.

Potential Implementation Plan

This CPG is the first of any Botox or FF evidence based guidelines for entry-level NPs. Furthermore, this CPG has recommended dosages and anatomical landmarks for each treatment to assist the mid level practitioner or RN. The Star Model of Knowledge Transformation and the JHEBPM were used to synthesize and convert knowledge

obtained from primary studies, delineate a rigorous systematic review of research, and provide best practice recommendations for the FRT assessment tool and CPG for novice NPs. The CPGs (Appendix B) and FRT assessment tool (Appendix D) are both valid and reliable user-friendly supplemental resources for an entry-level practitioner administer Botox or FFs. The findings of the systematic and integrative literature review; and developed CPG and adjunctive assessment tool will help promote quality patient care by assuring safety of patient and individualize treatment plan. This CPG and assessment tool should be utilized in the future to develop retroactive studies to evaluate the effectiveness of CPGs and adjunctive FRT assessment tool for entry-level practitioners while in the clinical setting.

CONCLUSION

Patient safety and individualized care is imperative when providing aesthetic treatments. The lack of evidence based guidelines for novice practitioner in the aesthetic field can result in various complications and poor patient outcomes. This quality improvement project has analyzed extensive literature reviews and expert recommendation consensus to develop evidence based guidelines and an adjunctive assessment tool. This guideline and assessment tool incorporate individualized treatment plan based on patient presentation. However, this clinical guideline is not intended to be a sole source of information or replace clinical judgment in administering Botox and facial fillers. Nonetheless, entry level NPs can adopt this guideline into their practice to improve quality patient care and optimal patient outcomes.

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APPENDIX A

EVALUATION FORMAT TO BE UTILIZED BY EXPERT

Name:

Profession:

Years of Experience with Botox and Hyaluronic Fillers:

Facial Rejuvenation Scale

- Wrinkle severity

Do you agree with the wrinkle severity assessment criteria assigned?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

- Mid facial aging

Do you agree with the age criteria and characteristic assigned?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

- Muscle Contraction Patterns for Botox

Do you agree with the different muscle contraction pattern for
glabella, frontalis, and crows' feet?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

Do you agree with the facial region for treatment of midface?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

Do you agree with the recommended treatment dosage for Botox?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

Do you agree with the recommended treatment dosage for Hyaluronic filler?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

- Do you agree the facial rejuvenation tool is easy to follow?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPGs)

- Do you agree the CPGs are written clearly and easy to follow?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

- Do you agree the CPGs will improve patient outcomes?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

- Do you agree the CPG will improve quality patient care for novice providers?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

- Do you agree the CPG will improve patient safety?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

- As a provider are you satisfied with the CPGs?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

- As an expert provider would the CPGs have been useful to you as a novice injector?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

- Would you recommend the CPGs to novice injectors?

() 4. Strongly Agree () 3 Agree () 2. Disagree () 1. Strongly Disagree

If disagree, what needs improvement?

Suggestions for Improvements:

APPENDIX B

CLINICAL PRACTICE GUIDELINES FOR ENTRY LEVEL NURSE PRACTITIONERS

These are the 2016-2017 recommendations for the administration of Botox and facial fillers for novice nurse practitioners. The recommendations outlined in this guideline are based on related literature reviews and expert opinions. This clinical guideline is intended to be a supplemental resource. Furthermore this clinical guideline is not intended to be a sole source of information or replace clinical judgment in administering Botox and facial fillers.

The 5 levels of hierarchy of evidence were adapted from Johns Hopkins Nursing on evidence-based practice (JHNEBP) model and guidelines (2014).

- Level I: is evidenced obtained from an experimental study or a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials (RCTs).
- Level II: is evidenced obtained from a quasi-experimental study, with or without meta-analysis
- Level III: is evidence obtained from non-experimental study, qualitative study, or meta-synthesis.
- Level IV: is non-research evidence obtained from systematic literature reviews or clinical practice guidelines.
- Level V: is non-research evidence obtained from quality improvement studies or expert opinion, or case studies.

The JHNEBP quality ratings of scientific evidence, systematic review, and expert opinion are categorized into 3 grades:

- Grade A: High quality.
- Grade B: Good quality.
- Grade C: Low quality or major flaws.

Pertinent evidence from each study or article was summarized in a table of evidence.

Botox and Dermal filler: Patient Teaching

- Erythema, edema, and ecchymosis are the most common injection side effects (Level 4, Grade B).
- Use ice to minimize swelling and bruising (Level 4, Grade B).
- Before treatment avoid products that inhibit clotting for several days (Level 5, Grade B).
- Sterile technique is recommended. Patient should remove all makeup before treatment (Level 5, Grade B).
- All patient should be counseled to avoid manipulating the injected area for several hours after treatment (Level 5, Grade B).

Botox: Assessment Plan for Glabella, Frontalis, and Crows' feet

- Refer to appendix for facial muscle patterns.
- Refer to Facial scale to grade severity of wrinkle.
- **Ethnicities:** Darker skin types, such as, African American (AA) Asians, Middle Eastern, and Hispanics will require less dosages of Botox due to less wrinkles, thicker skin, and more abundant collagen than Caucasians or fair skin (Level 4, Grade A).
- **Prescribe Antiviral drugs 1g of valacyclovir 1 week before treatment to avoid reactivation in patients diagnosed with herpes (Level 3, Grade A).**

Botox: Reconstitution Technique

- 100 units reconstituted with 2.5 ml of bacteriostatic normal saline (NS) (Level 4, Grade A)

Botox: Injection Technique

- 1 ml TB syringe or 30 gauge hypodermic needle with 1 ml syringe (Level 4, Grade B).
- **Start conservatively! Touchup can follow 2 weeks postprocedure (Level 4, Grade B).**

Botox: Glabella Injection Technique (See scale for standard dosages)

- **“U” pattern** most frequently seen in women. 5-injection site technique into procerus and corrugators (Level 5, Grade A).
- **“V” pattern** most frequently seen in males and second common in women. Higher intensity than any other pattern. 7-injection site technique. Higher doses at Procerus and corrugators (Level 5, Grade A).
- **Convergent “11” pattern** third common pattern in women and second in men. 2 to 4 injection site technique depending on severity at corrugators and medial orbicularis (Level 5, Grade A).
- **“Omega” pattern** fourth common pattern seen in men and women. 5-injection site technique with higher doses into the corrugators and orbicularis and lower doses into frontalis (Level 5, Grade A).
- **Inverted Omega “X” pattern** least frequently seen. 5-injection sites technique at procerus, depressor supercilli, and nasalis. Higher doses at procerus and lower doses at depressor supercilli (Level 5, Grade A).
- **Male vs. Female:** Men require higher dosage than female due to increase muscle mass strength (Level 4, Grade B).

Botox: Frontalis Injection Technique (See scale for standard dosages)

- **Total pattern** most common frequent pattern in both men and women. 9- injection site technique with higher dosages in the center and smaller doses laterally (Level 5, Grade B).
- **Medial pattern** second common frequent pattern in both men and women. 3 to 5 injection technique depending on severity of wrinkle. Refrain from treating outside midpupillary lines to avoid eyebrow ptosis (Level 5, Grade B).
- **Lateral pattern** occurs less frequently. Use low doses of toxin due to lower intensity of muscle contraction and to avoid interfering with eyebrow movement (Level 5, Grade B).
- **Inject 2cm above eyebrow to avoid brow ptosis** (Level 3, Grade A).

Botox: Crows' feet Injection Technique (See scale for standard dosages)

- **Medial pattern** inject using a 3 to 5 injection site pattern 1.5 to 2cm temporal to lateral canthus (Level 5, Grade A).
- **Lateral pattern** inject using a 3 to 5 injection site technique, 1.5 to 2cm below lateral canthus (Level 5, Grade A).
- **Do not inject below the zygomatic arch to avoid diffusion to zygomaticus major muscle causing paralysis in the lip and cheek** (Level 4, Grade A).

Botox: Contraindications (Level 4, Grade B)

- Pregnant/ Lactating women
- Attempting to become pregnant
- Neuromuscular weakness
- Inflammatory skin conditions
- Anticoagulation medications
- Quinine
- Calcium channel blockers
- Penicillamine
- Aminoglycoside antibiotics

Dermal Filler: Assessment Plan

- Refer to Facial scale to grade volume depletion
- **Prescribe Antiviral drugs 500mg of valacyclovir 1 week before treatment to avoid reactivation of herpes (Level 3, Grade A).**

Dermal filler: Technique for midface

- Use a 27gauge needle (Level 4, Grade A).
- Refer to appendix to outline treatment area for midface.
- **Aspirate before injecting to avoid compromising blood vessel which may cause tissue necrosis (Level 3, Grade A)**

Dermal filler: Treatment plan

- Refer to Facial Scale for proper dosage per midface region.
- Administer lower molecular weight hyaluronic acid (LMWH) such as, Voluma to build structural support and/or a high molecular weight hyaluronic acid for lines, grooves, and furrows, such as Juvederm and Restylane (Level 4, Grade A).
- When treating nasiolabial fold, restore volume to zygomatic, anteriomedial cheek, malar projection, and submalar area before correction nasiolabial area (Level 4, Grade A).
- Massage filler thoroughly to prevent unsightly clumping and effectively distribute product (Level 4, Grade B).
- **Start conservatively! Touchup can follow 2 weeks post procedure** (Level 4, Grade B).
- AAs are noted to have significant midface volume loss with age, as well as, heavier cheeks than Caucasians. Avoid treating nasiolabial folds and treat zygomatic arch, anteriomedial, malar projection, and submalar (Level 4, Grade B).
- Gender: When treating the female's cheeks the injector should stay on or above the zygomatic arch to prevent a masculine appearance. When treating the male's cheeks the injector should stay below the zygomatic arch to prevent a feminine appearance (Level 4, Grade B)

Dermal filler: Adverse reaction treatment plan

- If blanching, duskiness, or necrosis occurs immediately administer hyaluronidase as close to the injection site (Level 3, Grade A).

APPENDIX C

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Summary of Studies for Clinical Practice Guidelines for the Administration of Botox or Facial Filler

Study Design	Key variables and Level of Evidence	Simulation Studied	Study Focus & Outcomes	Conclusion
Consensus Recommendations for Asians Ahn, Kim, Kim, Rho, & Kim, 2013)	<u>Key variables</u> Consensus Recommendations, Asians, BTX-A <u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade B	Panel of experienced Korean Dermatologist	Purpose: To develop consensus recommendation on BTX-A treatment for Asians. Major Outcome: Recommendations addressed general question regarding treatment and provided specific guidelines on BTX-A procedure. Also compared consensus for Caucasians to Asians.	Guidelines provide resources for practitioner to perform safe and effective treatment for non-Caucasian skin type.
A retrospective analysis of case studies to evaluate frontal facial contraction patterns. (Braz & Sakuma, 2010)	<u>Key variables</u> BTX-A, muscle contraction, classification <u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade B	Retrospective analysis Private clinic 83 randomly selected patients 72 women and 11 men. Age 31-80 (mean age 48)	Purpose: To identify and classify frontal facial musculature contraction patterns in patient being treated for frontal facial wrinkles. Major outcomes: 3-contraction pattern were identified: Total, medial, and lateral. 50.6% of cases were total pattern. 25.3% were medial pattern. 24% were lateral pattern.	Identification and classification of frontal facial musculature contraction pattern provides a individualized treatment approach for each patient providing optimal outcomes.
Technique to restore Check Volume (Braz & Sakuma, 2011)	<u>Key Variables</u> Midface, HAF, Rejuvenation, recommendations <u>JHNEBP</u> Level IV Grade B	HAF 21G blunt needle	Purpose: Description of an innovative technique to restore lost volume in the midface. Major Outcome: To guide practitioner in the accurate placement of fillers.	The author has experience of 105 cases of injected HAF using described technique. Bruising last 3 to 5 days. Swelling last 24 hours.

<p>BTX-A, HAF dermal fillers, and combination therapy-consensus recommendation (Carruthers, Glogau, Blitzer, & Facial Aesthetic Consensus Group Faculty, 2008)</p>	<p><u>Key variables</u> Consensus recommendations, BTA-A, HAF</p> <p><u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade B</p>	<p>Multidisciplinary group of experts in aesthetic treatment Face was divided into upper, middle, and lower for the purpose of discussion.</p>	<p>Purpose: To review clinical implications of BTA-A and HAF and develop updated consensus recommendations for facial rejuvenation.</p> <p>Major Outcomes: Topic addressed included: Optimal technique; effect of sex, ethnicity, cultural ideals, and skin color; emerging trends. The group provided specific recommendation focused on tailoring treatment to the individual, treating multiple facial areas, and using a combination of products.</p>	<p>For optimal results a in-depth knowledge of facial aging and anatomy are important. Rejuvenation of facial feature involves muscle control, volume restoration, and recontouring.</p>
<p>Medical Literature Review (Funt & Pavici, 2013)</p>	<p><u>Key variables</u> Aesthetic medicine, complications</p> <p><u>JHNEBP</u> Level III Grade A</p>	<p>Medical literature review were reviewed by authors</p>	<p>Purpose: To describe potential adverse reaction and provide guideline on how to avoid or treat adverse reactions</p> <p>Major outcomes: Different facial fillers have different risk and injection technique. Majority of facial filler reaction are mild (edema or bruising) Serious adverse events are avoidable with proper technique and planning.</p>	<p>For quality care practitioner should have a in depth knowledge of facial anatomy, characteristic of product, indication, contraindication, and benefit.</p>
<p>Retrospective photographic analysis (Kim, Kim, Cho, Hwang, & Kim, 2014)</p>	<p><u>Key variables</u> Glabella, contraction pattern, BTA-A</p> <p><u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade A</p>	<p>139 Korean patient received BTX-A for the first time. Wrinkle pattern were identified and classified by a panel of experienced Korean dermatologist</p>	<p>Purpose: To identify and classify glabella wrinkle pattern for Asians for better treatment approach. Also to develop consensus recommendation for individual wrinkle patterns.</p> <p>Major outcomes: 5 patterns were identified. The classification of wrinkle patterns identified the important muscle in each classification.</p>	<p>Standardized treatment guidelines are imperative, particularly for novice practitioners. Appropriate training and knowledge will Inject active muscle with high doses and non-active muscle are spared or injected with low dose allowing effective and natural results. Classify glabella contraction patterns improves accuracy of treatment with BTX-A.</p>

Clinical practice guideline (Muhn, Rosen, Solish, Bertucci, Lupin, Dansereau, Weksberg, Remington, & Swift, 2012)	<u>Key variables</u> HAF, volumizing, facial rejuvenation <u>JHNEBP</u> Level IV Grade A	9 Canadian experts (8 dermatologist, one plastic surgeon)	Purpose: To provide guidelines which reflect extensive clinical experience and published literature. Major outcome: Global facial approach using volume restoration and facial contouring is essential to create a natural, youthful appearance.	Optimal facial rejuvenation is achieved by correcting volume loss at various layers of the facial anatomy.
Retrospective case study (Trindade de Almeida, Marques, Banegas, Bogdana, & Kadung, 2012)	<u>Key variables</u> BTX-A, muscle contraction, classification <u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade B	Pairs of photographs 2 groups 334 adult volunteers with specific movements. 36 previously treated individual after repeated treatment.	Purpose: To confirm glabella contraction patterns for an improved treatment approach and to analyze whether changes exist after repeated treatments. Major outcomes: 5 glabellar contractions were confirmed. Initial contraction pattern returned after waning of BTX-A toxin.	Inject active muscle with high doses and non-active muscle are spared or injected with low dose to achieve natural results. Classify glabella contraction patterns improves accuracy of treatment with BTX-A.
Consensus Recommendation of the use of OnaBTXA (Wolfgang, Philippe-Dormston, Bergfeld, Sommer, & the Onabotulinumtoxin Consensus group, 2012)	<u>Key variables</u> Consensus recommendations, BTA-A <u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade B	National expert panel for treatment of aesthetic. Long term clinical experience in aesthetic medicine. Consensus conference was held in Germany.	Purpose: To prepare consensus recommendation to guide beginners and also experienced users. Major outcomes: individuals views were not used; instead clinical experiences from leading expert were complied	Standardized treatment guidelines are imperative, particularly for novice practitioners. Appropriate training and knowledge will achieve quality patient care characterized by safety and professionalism.

Note. BTX-A = botulinum toxin type A; OnaBTXA = onabotulinum toxin type A; HAF = hyaluronic acid filler

Appendix D

FACIAL REJUVENATION TOOL

Facial
Severity

MILD

Wrinkles	Wrinkles not present at rest, Fine lines with facial expression	Wrinkles not present at rest, deep lines with facial expression.	Fine wrinkles present at rest, deeper with facial wrinkles	Deep wrinkles at rest, deep furrows with facial expressions.
Volume Loss	Age : 18 to 29 Fairly full midface	Age : 30 to 40 Mild loss of fullness in midface	Age: 40 to 50 Moderate loss of fullness in midface area.	Age: 50 to 60 Substantial loss of fullness in midface area

Botox	MUSCLE CONTRACTION	MILD/MODERATE	SEVERE
GLABELLA “U or V” pattern: 5 to 7 point injection sites	Procerus and Corrugators	Ethnicity /Gender Fair : W(10-20U), M(20-30U) Darker Skin : W(6-8 U), M(8 -12U)	Ethnicity /Gender Fair : W(20-30U), M(30-40U) Darker skin : W(12 U), M(16 U)
Convergent “11” 2 to 4 point injection sites	Corrugators, Medial Orbicularis	Fair : W(8-12U), M(12-16U) Darker skin : W(4-8 U), M(8-12 U)	Fair : W(12-20U), M(16-30U) Darker skin : W(8-12U), M(12-16 U)
Omega 5 injection sites	Corrugators, Orbicularis, Frontalis	Fair : W(10-20U), M(20-30U) Darker skin : W(5- 8.5 U), M(8.5-12U)	Fair : W(20-30U), M(30-40U) Darker Skin : W(8.512U), M(12-16U)
Inverted Omega or “X” 5 point injection sites	Procerus, Depressor supercilli, and Nasalis	Fair : W(10-20U), M(20-30U) Darker Skin : W(8-10 U), M(10-12U)	Fair : W(20-30U), M(30-40U) Darker skin : W(10-12U), M (12-16U)

FRONTALIS Total pattern: 9 point injection sites	Beyond midpupillary line	Fair: W(6-12U), M(6-12U) Darker skin: W(6-10U), M(10-14U)	Fair: W(12-15U), M(12-15U) Darker skin: W(13.5 U), M (17.5)
	Between midpupillary line	Fair: W(6-10U), M(6-10U) Darker skin: W(4-6U), M(6-10)	Fair: W(10-12U), M(10-12U) Darker skin: W(10 U), M(14 U)
	Outside midpupillary line	Fair: W(2-4U), M(2-4U) Darker skin: W (2-4U), M (4-6U)	Fair: W(4-6U), M(4-6U) Darker skin: W(6U), M(8U)
CROWS' FEET Medial/Lateral 2 to 5 injection sites per side		Ethnicity/Gender	Ethnicity/Gender
	Orbicularis oculi	Fair: W(10-20U/side), M(10-25U/side) Darker skin: W(2-4 U/side), M (4-6U/side)	Fair: W(20-30U/side), M(25-30U/side) Darker skin: W(7 U/side), M(10 U/side)
Hyaluronic Acid Fillers Midface Cheek	FACIAL REGION	MILD/MODERATE	SEVERE
		Gender	Gender
	Zygomatic Arch, anteriomedial, malar projection	W: 1 to 2 ml/side M: 0.5 to 1 ml/side	W: 3 ml/side M: 2 ml/side
Submalar Cheek	Submalar	W: 1 to 2 ml/side M: 0.5 to 1 ml/side	W: 3 ml/side M: 2 ml/side
Nasolabial Fold	Pyriiform fossa and nasiolabilal area	W: 0.5 to 1 ml/side M: 0.5 to 1 ml/side	W: 1+ ml/side M: 1+ ml/side

Figure 1: Carruthers (2012), Kim et al., (2004), Rzany et al., (2012), La Padula et al., (2016), Trindade de Almeida et al., (2012), Braz et al., (2010)

Appendix E

Table of Evidence

Summary of Studies for Facial Rejuvenation Tool

Study Design	Key variables and Level of Evidence	Simulation Studied	Study Focus & Outcomes	Conclusion
Descriptive Study (Carruthers, 2012)	<p><u>Key variables</u> Infraorbital hollows, cheek volume, cheek fullness, validated scale</p> <p><u>JHNEBP</u> Level III Grade A</p>	<p>359 men and women aged 25 to 66 were recruited and screen at three sites in 2009.</p> <p>Two updated scales: 148 men and women aged 25 to 71 were recruited at four sites in 2010.</p>	<p>Purpose: To objectively develop 3 grading scale for the infraorbital hollow, upper and lower cheek fullness to establish reliability</p> <p>Major Outcome: Interrater reliability was significant for infraorbital hollow, upper cheek, and lower cheek</p>	<p>Mid face scale are valid and reliable tools for the assessment of age related changes.</p> <p>Mid face rating scales are important in physician and patient</p>
A retrospective analysis of case studies to evaluate frontal facial contraction patterns. (Braz & Sakuma, 2010)	<p><u>Key variables</u> BTX-A, muscle contraction, classification</p> <p><u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade B</p>	<p>Retrospective analysis Private clinic 83 randomly selected patients 72 women and 11 men. Age 31-80 (mean age 48)</p>	<p>Purpose: To identify and classify frontal facial musculature contraction patterns in patient being treated for frontal facial wrinkles.</p> <p>Major outcomes: 3-contraction pattern were identified: Total, medial, and lateral. 50.6% of cases were total pattern. 25.3% were medial pattern. 24% were lateral pattern.</p>	<p>Identification and classification of frontal facial musculature contraction pattern provides a individualized treatment approach for each patient providing optimal outcomes.</p>
Non experimental study	<p><u>Key Variables</u></p>	<p>N = 20 Eleven postresidency</p>	<p>Purpose: Test reliability of a simple rating tool</p>	<p>RNKLS shows moderate to substantial reliability among</p>

(Kim , Reeck, Corey, and Maas, 2004)	Midface, HAF, Rejuvenation, recommendations <u>JHNEBP</u> Level III Grade B	physicians in aesthetic independently used Rated Numeric Kinetic Line Scale (RNKLS) of 20 photographs of frontalis, corrugator, orbicularis oculi	Major Outcome: RNKL Scale: 0 = No wrinkles 1 = Wrinkles not present at rest, fine lines with facial expressions. 2 = Wrinkles not present at rest, deep lines with facial expression. 3 = Fine wrinkles present at rest, deeper with facial wrinkles 4 = Deep wrinkles at rest, deep furrows with facial expressions.	observers, with high statistical significance. Valuable to assess outcome measures for research studies on hyperkinetic facial lines.
Non experimental Prospective study La Padula, Hersant, SidAhmed, Niddam, & Meningaud, 2016	<u>Key variables</u> Facial aging, Score, Rejuvenation medicine, Rejuvenation surgery, Aging, and Facial aging scale <u>JHNEBP</u> Level III Grade A	N = 1,000 1 month duration Mean age 44.7 (18 to 75) Female = 500; Male = 500 White 15 raters: 6 plastic surgeons, 3 dermatologist, 2 nurses, 2 psychologist, and 2 hospital secretaries.	Purpose: Develop a validate a new tool, the Face Objective Assessment Scale (FOAS) to evaluate aging sign severity. Major outcome: All scales exceeded criteria for reliability and validity. All patient were reassessed a month later by same rater. No rater variability was observed.	Adjunctive tool to assess complete initial and follow-up treatment.
Descriptive study (Rzany , Carruthers, Carruthers, Flynn, Geister, et al., 2012)	<u>Key variables</u> Midface, validated scale <u>JHNEBP</u> Level III Grade A	N=50 12 raters using 20 grading scales and the global face assessment	Purpose: To evaluate the reliability and validity of a complete face score and three global face assessment scales. Major outcome: Inter and intra rater reliability was high for complete face and estimated age and aesthetic treatment.	The scales are reliable and valid. Result suggest scale can help plan treatment for important areas of facial aging
	<u>Key variables</u>	Pairs of photographs	Purpose: To confirm glabella contraction patterns for an improved treatment approach	Inject active muscle with high doses and non-active muscle are

Retrospective case study (Trindade de Almeida, Marques, Banegas, Bogdana, & Kadung, 2012)	BTX-A, muscle contraction, classification	2 groups 334 adult volunteers with specific movements. 36 previously treated individual after repeated treatment.	and to analyze whether changes exist after repeated treatments. Major outcomes: 5 glabellar contractions were confirmed. Initial contraction pattern returned after waning of BTX-A toxin.	spared or injected with low dose to achieve natural results. Classify glabella contraction patterns improves accuracy of treatment with BTX-A.
	<u>JHNEBP</u> Level V Grade B			

Note. BTX-A = botulinum toxin type A; OnaBTXA = onabotulinum toxin type A; HAF = hyaluronic acid filler

APPENDIX F
MUSCLE CONTRACTION PATTERN

Glabella

“U” Pattern

“V” Pattern

“11” or “Corverging” Pattern

“Omega” Pattern

“X” Pattern

Frontalis

“Total” Pattern

“Medial” Pattern

“Lateral” Pattern

Crows’ Feet

“Medial/Lateral” Pattern

